

REVIEW

Translational Physiology

Pathogenetic mechanisms and therapeutic approaches of acute-to-chronic liver failure

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Abstract

Liver cirrhosis is the end stage of all chronic liver diseases and contributes significantly to overall mortality of 2% globally. The age-standardized mortality from liver cirrhosis in Europe is between 10 and 20% and can be explained by not only the development of liver cancer but also the acute deterioration in the patient's overall condition. The development of complications including accumulation of fluid in the abdomen (ascites), bleeding in the gastrointestinal tract (variceal bleeding), bacterial infections, or a decrease in brain function (hepatic encephalopathy) define an acute decompensation that requires therapy and often leads to acute-on-chronic liver failure (ACLF) by different precipitating events. However, due to its complexity and organ-spanning nature, the pathogenesis of ACLF is poorly understood, and the common underlying mechanisms leading to the development of organ dysfunction or failure in ACLF are still elusive. Apart from general intensive care interventions, there are no specific therapy options for ACLF. Liver transplantation is often not possible in these patients due to contraindications and a lack of prioritization. In this review, we describe the framework of the ACLF-I project consortium funded by the Hessian

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Ministry of Higher Education, Research and the Arts (HMWK) based on existing findings and will provide answers to these open questions.

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INTRODUCTION

Acute-on-chronic liver failure (ACLF) is a relatively common fatal disease with rapid deterioration (1), for which no specific therapies exist. Half of the patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis develop ACLF, and ~40% of them die within 28 days (1, 2). The pathogenesis of ACLF is poorly understood. Various precipitating events are believed to induce dysfunction or failure of the liver and other organs (3). The PREDICT study showed that in Europe bacterial infections and severe alcohol-associated hepatitis account for precipitating events in more than 96% of cases (4). These triggers lead to systemic inflammation and multiorgan failure defining ACLF, which is caused by complex organ interactions that are poorly understood. Systemic inflammation has been identified as the central pathomechanistic element in many studies (5–7), but the underlying mechanisms have not been sufficiently investigated to date.

Another key role in the pathogenesis of ACLF can be attributed to metabolic dysfunction (8, 9). It has also been hypothesized that vascular dysfunction, dysfunction of the intestinal barrier, and infection lead to the entry of large amounts of inflammatory molecules, so-called damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), and bacterial components into the bloodstream, so-called pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) (10). Thus, various general mechanisms that may lead to the features indicated earlier need to be investigated to identify the triggers and key mechanisms of the pathogenesis of ACLF from different perspectives, especially the acute phase reaction, the importance of the extracellular matrix (liver and kidney), and autophagy mechanisms in the immune response.

In addition to organ-specific mechanisms, such as the context- and time-dependent role of signaling pathways in the liver, kidneys, lungs, central nervous system (CNS), and blood cells, interactions between the organs involved plays a particularly important role in the development and severity of ACLF. A recent example is specific microRNAs that are synthesized in the liver but can cause vascular damage and heart failure distal to the site of synthesis (11). It is likely that these microRNAs are also involved in the interaction of the liver and heart in the framework of ACLF. Such multidimensional interplay of diverse mechanisms, including complex pleiotropic effects, can be investigated in computational, multiscale network models using bioinformatics and systems biology approaches to identify potential targets (signaling pathways and key factors) for preventive and therapeutic approaches.

To address these pending questions, data on gene expression, metabolic pathways, and protein interactions have to be integrated to generate biological models and to systematically explore key factors and mechanisms. In this way, specific approaches for the targeted modulation of immune dysregulation and resolution of inflammation can be identified to

clarify and understand the mechanism of ACLF, discover potential treatment targets, and improve the quality of life and outcome of patients with or at risk to develop ACLF.

ACUTE DECOMPENSATION OF LIVER CIRRHOSIS AND ACLF

Acute clinical deterioration in patients with cirrhosis often occurs through the development of ascites, jaundice, variceal bleeding, an acute episode of hepatic encephalopathy (HE), and/or acute bacterial infection (3, 12–15). These events define the clinical picture of acute decompensations (ADs) and thus often herald a new chapter in the clinical course of liver cirrhosis with precipitating events leading to development of ACLF. ACLF is a special entity developed from cirrhosis with AD, characterized by the additional development of (extrahepatic) organ failure.

Epidemiology and Socioeconomic Consequences

Liver cirrhosis, the end stage of all chronic liver diseases, affects more than 2 million Europeans every year, and an estimated 200,000 patients in Germany, of which young male patients are dominant, with increasing prevalence (16). The annual incidence of decompensated liver cirrhosis in Europe is around 800,000 patients. About 400,000 people develop ACLF (50%). Of these, around 160,000 (40%) die within 28 days since there are no specific therapy options (1, 2). For Germany, it has been shown that the additional costs of decompensated patients without liver transplantation amount to approximately €30,000 to €43,000 per year (17). ACLF is the reason for inpatient treatment in ~30% of all patients with liver cirrhosis. In particular, around 40% of younger patients (45–65 yr) develop ACLF during initial decompensation, and, with this age spectrum, affects the working part of the population, thus also having an economically relevant impact (1).

State of the Art on ACLF

ACLF was first characterized in the prospective CANONIC study with 1,343 patients from 29 European university hospitals (1). ACLF is divided into three severity levels according to The European Association for the Study of the Liver-Chronic Liver Failure (EASL-CLIF) criteria, based on the number of organ failures, and has been confirmed in various studies. Patients with no organ failure or organ failure other than kidney, on the other hand, are classified as no ACLF (1). Patients with an ACLF have a significantly increased 28- and 90-day mortality compared with no-ACLF patients with cirrhosis. With progression to ACLF, the already high mortality rate in patients with acute decompensation increases even further to 33–37% on *day 28* and 50% on *day 90* (Table 1) (1, 15, 18). The ACLF grade is a decisive factor for mortality, which is defined by the number of failing organs and can

Table 1. Acute-on-chronic liver failure grades and mortality

ACLF Grade	28-Day Mortality, %	90-Day Mortality, %
ACLF grade 1	19–23	32–41
ACLF grade 2	31–38	53–55
ACLF grade 3	74	78–83
ACLF (total)	33–37	50–51
No ACLF	1.9–5	10–12

Data from Refs. 1 and 18.

increase short-term mortality to over 70% (Table 1) (1, 18). Other definitions have been proposed such as the one by the Asian Pacific Association for the Study of the Liver, which however, can hardly be transferred to Europe and North America, since, among other factors, the most common ACLF patient group in these regions (decompensated cirrhosis with bacterial infections or active alcoholism) is not included in the definition (3). Despite the differences between the European, American, and Asian specialist societies, systemic inflammation and multiorgan failures in particular are undisputed (3, 13, 19). To specifically evaluate organ failure in ACLF, the chronic liver failure-sequential organ failure assessment (CLIF-SOFA) score and chronic liver failure-organ failure (CLIF-OF) score were established in international collaboration (20). Six different types of organ failure are included: liver, kidneys, coagulation, brain, lungs, and circulatory system, and thresholds for each individual organ failure were determined by a mortality of at least 15%. The PREDICT study, a prospective study with 1,310 patients from 48 European university hospitals, defined and characterized the various forms of AD (21) and the precipitating events that trigger ACLF (4). The so-called “pre-ACLF” was defined in patients with AD that develop to ACLF within 3 mo. Characteristics of pre-ACLF include organ dysfunction, severe confirmed bacterial infections, pronounced systemic inflammation, and high chronic liver failure-acute decompensation (CLIF-C AD) scores (21).

Research Demands

Currently, there are no specific treatment options for ACLF, other than intensive care management of the underlying organ failures and liver transplantation (12, 22). The pathomechanistic relationships underlying liver and organ failure are largely unknown. New experiments become necessary to generate relevant data in a systematic manner. These data need to be integrated in computational models to predict the system’s behavior and gain new insights into pathomechanisms.

ACLF TRIGGERS AND KEY MECHANISMS

State of the Art

The CANONIC and PREDICT study showed that the development and extent of ACLF depend on various factors (metabolites and lipids) that are related to systemic inflammation (1, 3, 4, 21). Studies on inflammatory markers in the CANONIC cohort have shown that systemic inflammation predates ACLF and is largely responsible for its development (5–7). These data from the CANONIC study could be confirmed in the

PREDICT study (4, 21). Systemic inflammation can be induced by exogenous and endogenous factors. The most important exogenous factor is the bacterial translocation (23, 24).

Bacterial Translocation

Interestingly, in ~20% of patients who developed ACLF and in 60% of patients with AD within the PREDICT cohort, no clear precipitating event could be identified (4). It is assumed that bacterial translocation would be the precipitating event in these cases, i.e., by releasing bacterial metabolites and bacterial components (PAMPs). PAMPs enter the bloodstream via an impaired intestinal barrier, which is triggered by exuberant inflammation, alcohol-associated hepatitis, or ischemia due to variceal hemorrhage. Interleukin-10 (IL-10) might mediate intestinal barrier disorder and favor bacterial translocation in patients with cirrhosis (Fig. 1). In addition, pathogenic properties of the pathogens probably favor bloodstream infection and thus the development of ACLF (10, 25, 26). The mechanism by which IL-10 might strengthen the intestinal barrier is presumably mediated by binding to the IL-10 receptor via Janus kinase 1 (JAK1)/tyrosine kinase 2 (Tyk2) and the downstream activation of the transcription factor signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (STAT3) and its phosphorylation. In addition, STAT3 is involved in the control of the inner mitochondrial membrane and the induction of reactive oxygen species (ROS), as well as in the regulation of cell-cell contacts (especially tight junctions). In human intestinal epithelial cells, microbial metabolites can induce an IL-10 receptor-dependent intestinal barrier disorder. Unpublished *in vivo* rat transcriptome data show that IL-10, Tyk2, and STAT3 mRNA levels are significantly elevated in the gut of ACLF animals. Consistently, elevated serum IL-10 levels have been found in patients with AD (6, 25).

Dysfunction of Cellular Components of Coagulation and Circulation

In addition to systemic inflammation, bacterial translocation can lead to platelet activation and thromboinflammation and thereby induce endothelial cell damage (27). Platelet activation can be mediated by prostanoids (e.g., thromboxane) (28, 29), which opens up possible therapeutic approaches. Transcription factors may play a crucial role in endothelial cell dysfunction. Endothelial cells (ECs) are adapted to the specific needs of the organs they supply (30–32). A classic example of such an organ-specific differentiation is the sinusoidal endothelial cells of the liver [liver sinusoidal endothelial cells (LSEC)]. The morphology and function of the LSECs allow for the efficient exchange of molecules between the bloodstream and liver parenchyma. In addition, the LSECs produce a repertoire of angiocrine factors (33) that orchestrate the organization (zoning) and regeneration of hepatocytes. Chronic liver damage leads to dedifferentiation (capillarization) of the LSECs and thereby promotes fibrogenesis (Fig. 1).

Platelets perform important pro- and anti-inflammatory functions, and platelet count is an important predictor of prognosis in patients with liver cirrhosis. The underlying mechanisms and their connection with ACLF are not yet understood. Activated platelets can drive inflammation via

Figure 1. Potential mechanisms and triggers of acute-on-chronic liver failure. ER, endoplasmic reticulum; Foxo, Forkhead-Box-Protein O; IL, interleukin; JAK, Janus kinase; MRGN, multidrug-resistant Gram-negative bacteria; STAT, signal transducer and activator of transcription. Image created with BioRender and published with permission.

microthrombosis, resulting in microischemia and direct immune cell activation. Increased platelet activation in the portal vein is associated with increased bacterial translocation and a more severe course of the disease (27). The importance of thrombocytes/immune cell complexes in the inflamed tissue for the course of inflammation has been already demonstrated (34, 35). These complexes can also be detected in the hepatic inflammatory foci in experimental cirrhosis. The pro- and anti-inflammatory effects of platelets are mediated by prostanoids (TXA₂ and PGE₂) and their receptors (TX₂R and EP_{2/4}) on macrophages and monocytes (34, 36, 37). The upregulation of PGE₂-generating enzymes (COX-2, mPGES-1) and the PGE₂ receptors (EP₁₋₄) in peripheral mononuclear cells has been demonstrated in an animal model for cirrhosis with repeated LPS injections as a trigger of ACLF. Accordingly, thromboxane-generating enzymes (COX-1, TXAS) are increasingly expressed in liver tissue (38).

Systemic inflammation with simultaneous immunodeficiency is a defining phenomenon in ACLF (39). Similar forms of immunodeficiency also occur in chronic inflammation, where inflammation resolution mechanisms fail. The resolution of inflammation is an active process aimed at restoring tissue homeostasis (40). Specific lipid mediators regulate both inflammation and its resolution. In particular, specialized proresolving lipid mediators (SPMs), such as lipoxins or resolvins, produced by 15-lipoxygenases (ALOX₁₅ and ALOX_{15B} in humans, Alox_{12/15} and Alox₈ in mice) have been associated with the resolution

of inflammation. ALOX₁₅ is mainly expressed by alternatively activated macrophages. It is required for the clearance of dying cells, an essential feature for inflammation resolution (41). However, proinflammatory effects of ALOX₁₅ have been described as well (42). The role of ALOX_{15B} during the production of SPMs is currently unclear. Recent data suggest a role for this enzyme in regulating cholesterol metabolism in macrophages, which affects, e.g., inflammatory chemokine production (43). Own data show that SPM lipoxin A₄ reduces inflammatory processes in an alcohol-associated liver injury model (44), but its role in ACLF remains elusive. Interestingly, plasma levels of Lipoxin A₅ were negatively associated with short-term mortality in patients with ACLF (45). Platelet activation as well as endothelial damage can in turn increase systemic inflammation and promote ACLF, which then manifests after a precipitating event (Fig. 1).

Furthermore, a stage-dependent lack of sphingosine-1-phosphate (S1P) as a central mediator of vascular barrier integrity and lymphocyte egress has been correlated with cirrhosis severity (46). S1P levels are determined, among other factors, by the presence of carrier proteins synthesized in the liver (albumin, HDL) and thus may represent a central link in cirrhosis-induced immunodeficiency.

Bacterial Infections

The PREDICT study examined the precipitating events that lead to AD and ACLF in more detail. It showed that,

above all, severe alcohol-associated hepatitis and confirmed bacterial infections, alone or in combination with other precipitants, are responsible for the development of ACLF (4). Nevertheless, according to current knowledge, the most common precipitating factor of ACLF is bacterial infections, primarily originating from spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP), secondary peritonitis, or pneumonia (47, 48). Infections with multidrug-resistant pathogens (particularly carbapenem-resistant gram-negative pathogens; MRGN) have also increased significantly over time and are closely associated with ACLF (47, 49). This new threat posed by MRGN has been classified as “critical” by the World Health Organization in the year 2017 (50). In ACLF in particular, infections with MRGN significantly worsen the prognosis (4, 47). In addition, the reduced antibiotic treatment options (e.g., due to carbapenem resistance, often in combination with other drug resistances) limit the therapeutic options dramatically, resulting in a significantly increased mortality in the event of infection (48, 49). Patients are often already colonized with MRGN before they are admitted to hospital, which promotes the development of bloodstream infections (BSIs) (Fig. 1). Understanding microbial infection processes is a key to new therapeutic options to prevent bacterial infection-triggered ACLF (51–54). The triggers known to date appear to initiate similar pathophysiological mechanisms.

Research Demands

Both soluble and cellular mediators of systemic inflammation specifically involved in ACLF have not been identified.

Their identification and neutralization may play a promising role in the prevention of ACLF (Fig. 2).

ETIOLOGIES OF CHRONIC LIVER DISEASES AND SPECIFIC ORGAN FAILURE IN ACLF

State of the Art

Obesity as a risk factor for steatosis and non-alcohol-associated steatohepatitis (NASH) is playing an increasing role worldwide and is more common in liver cirrhosis (55). In addition, obesity was also shown to be a risk factor for reoccurrence of infection and AD (56), of which infection is the most common precipitating event of ACLF. Although alcohol-associated liver disease is the most common underlying diagnosis in AD and ACLF, cirrhotic patients with obesity are more likely to develop ACLF than others. This is due to the rapid increase in the prevalence of the precursor non-alcohol-associated fatty liver disease (NAFLD), which affects up to one-third of the population in Western countries (16). Therefore, NAFLD is an increasing entity of chronic liver disease, which facilitates the development of ACLF.

Mitochondrial dysfunction is not only an important feature of NAFLD/NASH but also has been recently shown to be relevant during ACLF development (8, 57). In addition, dysregulation of autophagy mechanisms and an increase in endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress were found in ACLF (58). A number of factors such as lipotoxic stress, ER stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, ROS, and dysregulated autophagy may contribute to the progression of NAFLD, NASH, and

Figure 2. Pathophysiological mechanisms of acute-on-chronic liver failure and interaction of the liver with other organ systems.

cirrhosis (59). During the disease, the increase required in protein synthesis, folding, and repair results in ER stress. Selective autophagy of the ER-phagy is an important cellular mechanism to maintain tissue homeostasis under stress conditions (60, 61). We recently showed that the ER-phagy receptors of the FAM134 family regulate cellular fitness in neurons (62). FAM134BB is expressed in the liver mainly as the N-terminally truncated isoform FAB134B-2, where it regulates starvation-induced selective ER-phagy (63). Moreover, decreased hepatic FAM134B mRNA expression levels in NASH are recently reported (64).

Another liver-specific mechanism of ACLF is the reactivation of hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection in liver cirrhosis, which is the most common ACLF etiology in Asia (65, 66). Superinfection with hepatitis A (HAV) or hepatitis E (HEV) has also been described in ACLF and appears to be a relatively common trigger for ACLF in patients with existing hepatic injury (67). Coinfection of HBV with hepatitis delta (HDV) is considered the most aggressive viral hepatitis with only limited treatment options, and only limited data on its role in ACLF are available. Interestingly, the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, although not a typical hepatotropic virus, also indicates possible liver involvement in an infection and the influence of liver diseases on the clinical course of COVID-19 disease and appears to be able to trigger ACLF (68–72).

The presence of renal dysfunction has a decisive influence on patient survival, which is reflected in the classification of the ACLF (1). Kidney failure (AKI) is the most common organ failure of ACLF with an incidence of 50–80% in patients with ACLF and a significant impact on the disease course and mortality of ACLF. The presence of renal and/or cerebral dysfunction without other organ dysfunction doubles the risk of death (1). In the kidney, components of the extracellular matrix and the signaling molecules regulated by it could serve as triggers for an excessive inflammatory reaction (73). Both, circulatory dysfunction and a systemic and renal inflammation seem to be the key mechanisms in the development of ACLF with AKI. In the liver, blood, and kidneys of ACLF models, we found a significantly increased level of biglycan, a proteoglycan of the extracellular matrix, which induces and amplifies sterile or pathogen-mediated inflammation as an autonomic trigger (73). This occurs via binding of biglycan to the coreceptor CD14 to elicit proinflammatory signaling through Toll-like receptors (TLR)-2 and TLR-4 (74, 75), which are the most relevant pattern recognitions receptors sensing DAMPs and PAMPs in ACLF (76–78).

In the brain, neuroinflammation plays a prominent role, leading to the development of hepatic encephalopathy (HE). HE is the main neurological complication of liver cirrhosis and an important criterion for the definition of ACLF. HE develops either covertly or with a variety of symptoms ranging from mild cognitive impairment and behavioral changes to coma. The pathophysiology of HE is insufficiently researched, complicating the prevention and differentiation, especially of covert HE. Cytotoxic cerebral edema, e.g., mediated by astrocyte swelling (“astrogliopathy”) with an increased ammonia level, as well as neuroinflammation are responsible for the degree of severity and the prognosis. Proinflammatory mediators most likely originate from cerebral endothelial cells, the first resident brain cells to be exposed to ammonia or LPS, and microglia, the brain’s resident immune cells. A strong regulation of

the sphingolipid signaling pathway has been shown in an animal model of LPS-endotoxemia (79). After stimulation of astrocytes with inflammatory mediators, there is a significant increase in sphingosine-1-phosphate (S1P) receptors and sphingolipid-metabolizing enzymes (79–81). In addition, the S1P signaling pathway appears to be a potent and direct regulator of pathological astrocyte responses (82, 83).

Pulmonary dysfunction was reported with a high prevalence in patients with liver cirrhosis, ranging from 4% to 41% (84, 85), and has a very poor prognosis (86, 87). The mechanism underlying the high risk of developing ACLF and mortality of pulmonary dysfunction is unclear and likely multifactorial. Even with chronic liver disease, pneumonia leads to a 3.6-fold increase in mortality, which may be one of the underlying reasons (88). The pathophysiology of respiratory infections in ACLF is still unclear. In view of the above-average mortality of ACLF patients with pneumonia, understanding these relationships is of great importance to clinical practice. Previous work has shown that influenza virus infections and COVID-19 can be precipitating factors in ACLF that lead to reduced survival (66, 89). In addition, patients with community-acquired pneumonia and chronic liver disease have a higher mortality rate (88, 90). In lung tissue from an ACLF animal model, we observed increased expression of genes in the lungs that are indicative of pulmonary inflammation and changes in pathogen recognition.

Research Demands

So far, there are no conclusive pathophysiological explanations for any of these observations and connections. The underlying molecular and organ-specific mechanisms for the failure of one or more organs are not yet clear (Fig. 2).

ORGAN INTERACTION AND ASPECTS OF SYSTEMS MEDICINE

State of the Art

In addition to the exogenous triggers, systemic inflammation can also be induced by DAMPs, such as histones, HMGB1, biglycan, or DNA. It has been shown that such triggers for organ failure can originate from the liver (91) and the fact that transplanting the liver leads to a resolution of multi-organ failure after ACLF supports this hypothesis. The actual target of the inflammatory response may differ due to the different types of stimuli. Although infection-driven inflammation seeks to prevent bacterial spread, DAMP-induced inflammation aims at tissue repair. An “excessive” inflammatory response to these stimuli can damage tissues and organs and lead to (multiple) organ failure through organ interaction.

Circulatory and endothelial dysfunction are features of liver cirrhosis that are associated with the level of systemic inflammation and a poorer prognosis in ACLF. Endothelial cells are the first to be exposed to circulating inflammatory markers and therefore play an important role in interorgan communication. With the secretion of transcription factors, they react to external signals that are regulated, for example, microRNAs synthesized in the liver that regulate cell-specific metabolic functions and trigger an inflammatory reaction in the heart and blood vessels (92, 93). Moreover, activation of

the transcription factor KLF2 via statins prevents the development of ACLF in animal models (94). The KLF2 signaling pathway is also critically regulated by microRNAs in various tissues (heart, vascular, and kidney).

The inflammatory response to circulating markers depends on many regulatory molecules. In the case of IL-22, specific modulation of receptor function and downstream STAT1/3 signaling is critical for its function in various target cells and organs (intestine, liver, and lung) (95). IL-22 is likely a key cytokine in the immune dysregulation of ACLF, is partly gut-derived, and can serve both, pathogenic and hepatoprotective functions. It has been shown that high IL-22 levels are associated with decompensated liver cirrhosis, ACLF, and increased mortality (95–98). Evidence suggests that IL-22 and lipid metabolism are closely linked and that the lipid composition of cell membranes of IL-22 target cells may influence the IL-22 signaling phenotype, and that the IL-22-STAT1/3 signaling balance and IL-22 receptor conformation could be used therapeutically (99–102). However, the role of IL-22 in the progression of ACLF, particularly as a function of target cell and tissue/organ and, for example, a changing lipid environment, remains to be characterized in more detail.

Systemic inflammation can induce organ dysfunction and failure through various mechanisms, including circulatory dysfunction, organ hypoperfusion, and tissue ischemia. The circulatory dysfunction in liver cirrhosis is characterized by hypocontractility of the extrahepatic vessels and increased cardiac output, which is also associated with the development

of ACLF (103). Due to the large number of mechanisms and organs involved, it is necessary to consider the entire system in computational network models at different levels of abstraction, incorporating parts of a whole together to identify key factors in ACLF development.

In many patients with liver cirrhosis, there is also immunosuppression in addition to the excessive immune reaction. The PREDICT study was able to show for the first time that nontargeted or insufficiently broad antibiotic therapy is associated with a significantly higher ACLF rate (4), with ACLF itself massively increasing the infection rate, particularly the rate of BSI (47, 104). The microbiome altered by antibiotic therapy probably plays an important role here. The underlying molecular mechanisms behind this are extremely complex and have not been elucidated yet. It is shown, however, that the interaction of various extrahepatic organ failures leads to an exponential increase in mortality of up to 90% in 28 days in ACLF. In particular, BSI after bacterial and/or fungal translocation through the intestinal epithelium is a common complication in patients with ACLF and is associated with high morbidity and mortality (105–107). The worldwide increase in infections with multidrug-resistant pathogens further complicates the prevention and treatment of BSI in these patients (108). Frequent antibiotic exposure in the clinics leads to further clonal expansion of resistant pathogens with progressive overgrowth in the gut microbiota. This progressive imbalance encourages further breakdown of the physiological

Figure 3. Role model for the identification of mechanisms leading to the development of ACLF. The integration of human and experimental data require rigorous research efforts both at the cellular/molecular and systemic level. ACLF, acute-on-chronic liver failure.

intestinal wall barrier and translocation of bacteria and fungi into the bloodstream.

Research Demands

Clinicians often face domino-like organ failures in patients with ACLF. So far, it is not clear how these organs communicate with each other, or how this multidimensional interaction cascade can be stopped in ACLF (Fig. 2). Disturbances (perturbations) of a state can affect the entire organism via multiple, directly or indirectly linked processes at different levels (molecules, cells, and tissues/organs) and lead to a transition to a new state, e.g., to acute decompensation or ACLF. By integrating genomic sequence data with functional and dynamic data, such as gene expression, metabolic pathway, and protein interaction data, underlying biological processes can be modeled and characterized in detail. Computational network models and statistical models can describe such highly complex relationships. By integrating multidimensional data at different levels, this enables systems medicine approaches using different modeling techniques, for example, Petri nets (96, 97) or agent-based approaches (98, 99).

CONCLUSIONS

ACLF is a prevalent and deadly syndrome occurring upon liver cirrhosis, which is characterized by its complexity. Identification of mechanisms leading to the development of ACLF requires rigorous research efforts both at the cellular/molecular and systemic levels, which is best achieved by interdisciplinary consortia (Fig. 3).

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DISCLAIMERS

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

R.S., W.G., C.W., and J.T. conceived and designed research; R.S., C.W., and J.T. prepared figures; R.S., W.G., C.W., and J.T. drafted manuscript; R.S., W.G., A.B., B.B., S.C., I.D., S.D., G.G., F.R.G., E.H., E.H., V.A.J.K., S.K., I.K., H.M., V.M., K-H.P., R-I.K., A.P., G.R., K.S., M.H.S., H.S., T.T., M.V-N., M.J.G.T.V., A.W., P.J.W., S.Z., C.E., A.i., L.S., C.W., and J.T. edited and revised manuscript; R.S., W.G., A.B., B.B., S.C., I.D., S.D., G.G., F.R.G., E.H., E.H., V.A.J.K., S.K., I.K., H.M., V.M., K-H.P., R-I.K., A.P., G.R., K.S., M.H.S., H.S., T.T., M.V-N., M.J.G.T.V., A.W., P.J.W., S.Z., C.E., A.i., L.S., C.W., and J.T. approved final version of manuscript.

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